

PROBLEMS OF APPLYING THE RULES OF THE INSTITUTE OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW TO BIG DATA RELATIONS

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The relationship between Big Data and intellectual property rights is complex and multifaceted, at the heart of which lies the question of the right to own and use information. Traditional intellectual property rights mainly protect the results of creative activity (works, inventions, designs, etc.) and means of individualization (such as trademarks). Big Data, on the other hand, is often not a creative work, but a collection of facts, observation results, sensor data, and similar raw data. In legal doctrine, facts and information themselves are not considered property - in US law, for example, in the case of the Supreme Court's **Feist v. Rural** states that simple facts are not protected by copyright. Therefore, a large dataset itself (if it does not have an original structure in terms of copyright) cannot be a direct object of copyright¹.

However, the value of Big Data collection and the benefits derived from it are reflected in the labor and resources spent on its creation and collection. In law, various approaches are applied to protect such a product of labor. In the experience of the European Union, this issue has been resolved **through the introduction of "sui generis" database law**, that is, there is a mechanism for protecting databases collected without original creative selection with a separate property right. In the United States, there is no such exclusive right; instead, **contractual** and **commercial secrecy** institutions and, in some cases, **misappropriation** are applied².

The application of the design of the intellectual property law institution in the context of Big Data refers to the adaptation of existing legal frameworks - for example, the principles of copyright, patent law provisions, database protection mechanisms, methods of protecting commercial secrets - to the conditions of use and protection of Big Data. There are various conceptual approaches to this in the scientific literature. While some scholars proposed introducing a separate "data ownership right" for Big Data, others approach this approach cautiously, warning that such a new right may clash with the protection of personal data and freedom of innovation. For example, a German lawyer **Thomas Hoeren** poses the question "if new property rights to data are introduced, does this

contradict personal data protection laws?" In fact, Big Data often includes personal data, and the transfer of ownership rights to them can affect the fundamental rights of the subjects of this data. For this reason, a new category of intellectual property for Big Data has not yet been created at the international level, but the problem is being solved by integrating existing legal instruments³.

Another theoretical issue is the emphasis on the concepts of use and control over ownership. In the Big Data era, controlling access to and restricting access to data is becoming more important than acquiring property rights. Researchers note that in Big Data relations, the paradigm "**transition to ownership to access**" (**ownership to access**) is observed. That is, from an economic point of view, it has become more important to determine who, when, and under what conditions can access them than the data itself. Therefore, the legal strategy of large data owners is often aimed at restricting the confidentiality of information (commercial secrecy) and the dissemination of information on a contractual basis. Along with contractual restrictions, technical protection measures (e.g., **DRM**, encryption, API access restrictions) are also applied. All of this expands the traditional understanding of intellectual property rights, demonstrating that it is being mobilized to protect Big Data assets.

Below is an analysis of how individual areas of Big Data and intellectual property law - copyright, patents, sui generis rights of databases, commercial secrets, etc. - are affected, legal problems arising from Big Data in these areas, and ways to solve them.

Copyright traditionally protects works of literature, art, and science, that is, expressions that are the result of the author's creative activity. In the context of Big Data, copyright is relevant in several ways:

1. Copyright status of a dataset: If the database or dataset contained in Big Data has a creative character in terms of selection or regulation, then it can be a copyrighted **compilation (collection work)**. For example, if a database of statistical data is compiled in a certain original way, then in accordance with the legislation of Uzbekistan, such a database is also recognized as an object of copyright. In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Copyright and Related Rights," the concept of a database is defined as "a set of systematized information expressed in objective form, which can be found and processed using a computer," and is provided as an object of copyright. However, in practice, Big Data datasets are often collected automatically, without creative selection (for example, data collected by scanning websites). In such cases,

copyright does not grant protection rights to the contents of such a collection, since it does not contain the original creative layer necessary for authorship.

2. Copyrighted materials in Big Data: A Big Data collection may include content from various sources, such as copyrighted works in the form of text, images, audio, or video. For example, **text and data mining technologies (Text and Data Mining, TDM)** are used to analyze corpora of scientific articles or literary texts - in this process, software tools can copy and analyze thousands of copyrighted texts. From a legal point of view, this copy is a reproduction, which is prohibited without the permission of the copyright holder according to the usual rules of copyright. At this point, a legitimate question arises whether the use of such works in Big Data for research or analytical purposes violates copyright. In recent years, many countries have introduced special exceptions to copyright as a solution to this issue. For example, **Articles 3 and 4 of the Digital Single Market Directive adopted by the European Union in 2019** established exceptions for research institutions and other users that do not consider the TDM process a copyright infringement. Based on these exceptions, researchers and AI algorithms can analyze large text and image corpora without obtaining separate permission from copyright holders (only access to the source must be unlimited). Similarly, in 2018, Japan amended its legislation, declaring automatic data analysis for any purpose (including commercial) legal. In the USA, although there is no such clear normative exception, in judicial practice, TDM is permitted with the help of **the "fair use" doctrine**. In particular, the digitization and indexing of millions of books within the framework of **the Google Books project** was recognized as not infringing on copyright. In the USA, the court recognized this as scientific-analytical and transformative use, that is, fair use. Thus, in the process of analyzing Big Data, opportunities for use are being created that do not contradict copyright. However, at the same time, the scope of these exceptions may vary in each jurisdiction; for example, in Europe there is a complete exception only for scientific research and some general purposes, while for the general public, a limited (if the purpose is not commercial) exception is applied.

3. Works created using Big Data and copyright: Big Data is often processed by artificial intelligence systems, and in some cases, artificial intelligence can create new information or even works. For example, the emergence of texts and drawings written by generative AI as a result of machine interpretations learned from Big Data corpora (a phenomenon observed today) - the issue of applying copyright to these works is also causing discussions.

Copyright is usually tied to a human author, and the question remains open whether an independent "creation" of artificial intelligence is protected by copyright. The US Copyright Office recently confirmed that only works created by humans are eligible for copyright, while it announced it would not grant copyright to artificial intelligence generation. Europe and other jurisdictions are also not yet unanimous in this regard. Although this issue is not directly part of the Big Data legal relationship, it is important because the probability that secondary products created using Big Data are not covered by copyright may affect the commercial value of Big Data projects. For example, if a summary or report automatically generated using big data analysis cannot be copyrighted, there is a risk that competitors will freely copy it. This can reduce the motivation of investors and creators. Some scientific doctrines offer specific solutions for such cases (for example, a special right with a very short additional protection period), but there is currently no practical solution.

